

Sterility percentage showed a high direct effect on grain yield (0.928). Direct negative effects were observed for number of panicles/m², panicle length, and 1,000-grain weight. Other characters, such as panicles/m² did not show any direct effect on yield.

Filled grains per panicle and sterility percentage appear to be the most reliable indices for selection under saline conditions. □

Yield and yield attributes of rice cultivar Mahsuri grown at different salinity levels in farmers' fields, Khambhat taluka, Gujarat, India.

Salinity level ^a	EC (dS/m)	ESP ^b	Panicles (no./hill)	Sterility (%)	Unfilled grains hill (g)	Dry filled grains/hill (g)	Straw/hill (g)	Biological yield/hill (g)	Harvest index
Normal	1.4	0.81	15	16.9	1.66	27.14	10.3	39.1	0.69
Low	6.3	4.6	5.4	10.3	1.35	8.2	10.3	19.1	0.40
Moderate	11.8	6.9	4.8	29.7	0.45	7.1	8.83	12.1	0.33
Severe	25.6	12.0	13.2	80.6	3.4	2.7	14.6	23.1	0.11
LSD (0.05)	9.1	6.8	4.9	50.6	1.64	9.9	4.3	12.6	0.13

^aCategorized by farmers. ^bExchangeable sodium percentage.

Performance of rice cultivar Mahsuri at different salinity levels

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In villages lying between 22°24' and 22°30' N and 72°25' and 72°37' E in

Khambhat taluka, Kheda district, Gujarat, India, soil degradation caused by waterlogging has resulted in rice becoming the principal crop. This has further aggravated the salinity problem and waterlogging. Cultivable fields have been affected by salinity. We collected soil samples and rice plants (Mahsuri) from saline-affected fields to see the effect of soil degradation on the crop.

Soil analysis showed that EC values

increased from 1.4 to 25.6 dS/m. The increased salinity caused a reduction in all rice yield parameters measured (see table). The biological yield under severe soil salinity was higher than under less salinity because of the increase in straw weight per hill. Sterility increased in response to increasing salinity. Salinity decreased economic yield by 70, 74, and 90% at EC of 6.3, 11.8, and 25.6 dS/m. □

Manifestation of heterosis in rice (Oryza sativa L.) in a saline environment

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We studied the expression and magnitude of heterosis in rice in a saline environment.

Five varieties and strains were crossed during 1982:

1. NIAB RICE (NR-I)/C23-3-1
2. NR-I/IR6
3. NR-I/Jhona 349

4. Jhona 349/IR6
5. IR6/Basmati 370

The F₁ and the parents were grown in NIAB fields in Jun 1983. Six-week-old seedlings were transplanted into drainable concrete field basins (6 × 6 × 1 m). For artificial salinization, 4 commercial salts — MgCl₂, NaCl, CaCl₂, Na₂SO₄—were mixed with soil at ratios of 1:4:5:10. Desired salinity was further achieved by infrequent irrigation with tubewell water (saline sodic). In the randomized complete block design with 4 replications, seedlings were transplanted at 1/hill and 20-cm

spacing. At least 20 plants/ replication were observed. Yield and 1,000-grain weight were recorded after drying grains to 14.0% moisture. To test the performance of F₁ hybrids, heterosis was calculated over that of the better parent.

Heterosis was variable and inconsistent not only for plant attributes but also for crosses (see table).

No heterosis was observed for number of primary branches per panicle and panicle fertility percentage in the saline environment.

The greatest heterosis for yield per

Heterosis estimates (%) in F₁ over better parents for yield and yield components of rice under salt stress.^a NIAB, Faisalabad, Pakistan, 1982.

Cross	Heterosis (%)								
	Plant height	Productive tillers plant	Panicle length	Primary branches/panicle	Grains/panicle	Total florets/panicle	Panicle fertility percentage	1000-grain weight	Yield per plant
NR-I/C23-3-1	+0.6*	-17.0**	-2.2	+7.5	+44.4**	+25.9**	-2.1	-1.6	+78.0**
NR-I/IR6	+5.1*	+6.3	+7.8**	+3.3	+25.3**	+30.9**	-7.6**	+8.9**	+87.5**
NR-I/Jhona 349	+3.2*	-25.0**	-1.7	-9.2	+16.5**	+4.1	-2.8	-3.7**	-30.0**
Jhona 349/IR6	+12.4**	+54.8**	+6.9**	+9.4	0.2	+34.4**	-33.9**	+19.7**	+154.4**
IR6/Basmati 370	-13.8**	-40.8**	-4.7**	+0.9	+20.4**	+13.6**	+0.3	+11.6**	+13.9**

^a* = significant at P=0.05, ** = significant at P=0.01. pH 9.0, E_c 6.5 dS/m at 25°C, sodium adsorption ratio = 22.2.

plant was 154.4% for Jhona 3491/IR6. This was based on simultaneous heterosis in plant height, number of productive tillers per plant, panicle

length, total florets per panicle, and 1,000-grain weight. Heterosis for yield for the best 4 crosses varied greatly from 13.9 to 154.4%.

Results indicate the potential for harnessing hybrid vigor in the development of relatively salt-tolerant strains of rice. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

CN704-7-3, a new variety for rainfed deepwater areas in eastern India

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Based on national performance in 1984-86, the 1986 annual rice workshop at Hyderabad recommended CN704-7-3

(IET9060) from the cross Pankaj/CN540 developed at RRS, for areas where water stagnates up to 100 cm during wet season (kharif) in West Bengal and Bihar. In six state adaptive trials in 1982-85, CN704-7-3 outyielded the checks Tilokkachari and Mahsuri by 25% (see table). CN704-7-3 yielded better than check 1 at several water depths (see figure).

CN704-7-3 is photoperiod sensitive

Performance of CN704-7-3 in state and national trials. India, 1982-86.

Trial and year	Site	Max water depth ^a (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
			CN704-7-3	Local check		
State adaptive	1982	Chinsurah	70	3.2	2.4	Tilokkachari
		Nimpith	60	3.6	2.8	Mahsuri
	1983	Hooghly	75	3.8	2.9	Mahsuri
		Chinsurah	75	3.9	2.9	Tilokkachari
	1984	Narendrapur	55	3.4	2.6	Mahsuri
1985	Burdwan	75	3.7	2.6	Mahsuri	
National PVT-5	1984	Cuttack	na	2.5	1.0	CR210-1018
		Bhubaneswar	25	2.0	1.4	OR1 104
		Patna	65	2.1	1.7	Janki
		Sabour	na	3.2	3.0	Janki
UVT-5	1985	Cuttack	na	3.3	3.1	CR1030
		Bhubaneswar	na	1.8	2.0	Khajuriachaur
		Chinsurah	65	3.0	2.0	Tilokkachari
		Karimgunj	na	3.2	2.5	na
		Malda	70	3.6	3.0	CN540
		Ghagraghat	60	2.9	2.0	Madhukar
		Patna	na	2.7	1.8	na
		Arundhutinagar	na	4.9	4.5	Pizam
Physiology screening	Calcutta	60	4.7	4.6	Pankaj	
	Chinsurah	65	2.1	0.9	Mahsuri	
	Cuttack	55	2.7	2.2	CR1018	
	Patna	50	3.4	3.0	IET8879	
	Titabar	50	3.5	3.1	Manoharsali	
UVT-5	1986	Chinsurah	110	3.0	1.1	TCA212
		Malda	62	3.6	3.2	CN540
		Pusa	85	2.2	1.8	TCA214
		Ranital	65	2.2	1.7	CR1030
		Faizabad	80	1.3	2.0	Pankaj
Physiology screening	Cuttack	50	4.3	3.4	CR1018	
	Patna	50	3.2	2.2	Janki	
Mean (30 sites)			3.1	2.4		

^a na = data not available.

Yield performance of CN704-7-3 in different water regimes. Chinsurah, India, 1982-86.

and flowers 26-30 Oct. Depending on water depth, it reaches 150-175 cm height with 10-12 tillers/hill. The variety has very good submergence tolerance, kneeing ability, and drought tolerance at early vegetative stage. The panicle is about 22 cm long with good exertion, each accommodating about 175 grains. Grain is medium and bold (length-5.6 mm, breadth-2.8 mm, L:B-2.0) and 1,000-grain weight is 25 g. It possesses yellow hull at maturity, red kernel, and strong seed dormancy. The variety is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and moderately susceptible to blast.

CN704-7-3 yielded 3.1 t/ha (2.4 t/ha for check) in 30 locations and has been recommended for minikit demonstration trials in farmers' fields. □

Improved basmati donors

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Traditional basmati rices have tall plants, droopy leaves, high lodging tendency, relatively low grain weight,